

FIRM ATTRIBUTES AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED FIRMS IN NIGERIA

Sanni Philip Shakede¹ & Obomeile Cyril (PhD)²

^{1,2} Department of Accounting and Finance, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria
Formerly Samuel Adegboyege University

¹ Philipsanni77@gmail.com / 08033242630

² cymek2003@yahoo.com / 08069211489

Abstract

This study examines the impact of firm-specific attributes on the financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria, with particular focus on firm size, firm age, and leverage. Using panel data covering the period from 2014 to 2023 for a sample of selected Nigerian listed companies, the study employed Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (POLS) regression to determine the relationship between the identified firm characteristics and financial performance, proxied by Return on Assets (ROA). The findings revealed that firm age has a significant positive effect on financial performance, suggesting that older firms tend to benefit from accumulated experience and operational efficiency. In contrast, firm size negatively impacts financial performance, indicating possible inefficiencies or structural challenges in managing large-scale operations. Leverage was also found to have a strong negative effect, implying that excessive debt undermines profitability. The study recommends that firms should strategically manage growth to avoid inefficiencies, utilize debt cautiously, and leverage their operational experience to improve performance.

Key Words: Firm Attributes, Financial Performance, Firm Size, Firm Age, Leverage, Listed Firms.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20283915

1 INTRODUCTION

Firm attributes is a widely studied concept in the analysis of corporate financial performance, particularly in research examining firm growth, maturity, and life-cycle dynamics. The underlying assumption is that older firms accumulate knowledge, capabilities, and institutional experience that can translate into enhanced efficiency, stability, and profitability over time (Rossi, 2016). Such firms are presumed to have undergone various economic cycles, gained strategic insights, and built robust networks, giving them a comparative advantage over younger firms.

Ilaboya and Ohiokha (2016) also emphasized that firm age confers access to valuable resources such as capital, market intelligence, and operational formalization factors that collectively support improved financial performance. This suggests that longevity may correlate positively with profitability, particularly in environments like Nigeria where business survival is a challenge due to infrastructural and regulatory constraints.

Firm-specific attributes, especially firm size and firm age, are increasingly recognized as important determinants of performance outcomes. Larger firms often enjoy operational advantages such as access to finance, improved risk diversification, and economies of scale, which may enhance profitability (Aladejebi, 2021). Similarly, older firms may benefit from accumulated experience, reputation, and learning curves,

thereby improving their operational stability and financial outcomes (Onyekwelu & Ugwuanyi, 2020). However, the performance advantages linked to size and age are not guaranteed, as they may be offset by bureaucratic inefficiencies or structural rigidity.

Despite these theoretical expectations, empirical findings on the relationship between firm size, firm age, and performance remain inconclusive, especially in the African context. For instance, Odugbesan and Ajao (2022) found that firm size significantly influenced financial performance in Nigerian manufacturing firms, while their study found no consistent impact of firm age. In contrast, Egbunike and Ejeabasi (2020) reported a weak correlation between both firm size and age and profitability in a multi-sectoral analysis of listed firms. These discrepancies underscore the need for further investigation using robust and updated datasets.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite extensive literature on the determinants of firm performance, there remains no consensus on the effect of firm size and age, especially within emerging economies such as Nigeria. Some empirical studies support a positive relationship between firm size and financial performance, arguing that larger firms benefit from economies of scale, diversified revenue streams, and better access to credit facilities. For example, Odugbesan and Ajao (2022), in their study of Nigerian manufacturing firms, found that larger firms consistently outperformed smaller ones in terms of their return to asset (ROA) and return to equity (ROE), attributing this to operational efficiency and market power. Similarly, Ogundipe et al. (2020) reported that firm size had a significant positive effect on financial performance among firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, suggesting that size enables access to better financing and resource mobilization.

Conversely, other researchers argue that increased size may lead to bureaucratic inefficiencies and loss of flexibility, which negatively affect performance. Egbunike and Ejeabasi (2020) observed that beyond a certain threshold, larger Nigerian firms experienced diminishing financial returns, possibly due to over-centralization and slow decision-making. The evidence on firm age is equally mixed. While Ilaboya and Ohiokha (2016) found that older firms in Nigeria showed superior financial performance due to accumulated experience and stronger stakeholder relationships, Loderer et al. (2017) and Coad et al. (2018) suggested that aging firms might become complacent or resistant to innovation, ultimately weakening profitability. These conflicting findings reveal that the relationship between firm attributes and performance is context-dependent and may vary across sectors, regulatory environments, and stages of economic development. Therefore, more context-specific research is needed to clarify these dynamics in Nigeria's evolving corporate landscape.

However, the relationship between firm age and financial performance is not always straightforward. Several recent studies have raised concerns about the direction and nature of causality in this relationship. Loderer, Stulz, and Waelchli (2017), for instance, suggest that increasing firm age could be associated with declining efficiency due to inertia, bureaucratic complexity, and resistance to innovation. Similarly, Coad, Daunfeldt, and Halvarsson (2018) argue that performance may plateau or even decline as firms age, especially if they fail to adapt to changing market conditions. These perspectives introduce the possibility of reverse or non-linear causality, where not only does firm age influence financial performance, but performance outcomes may also affect a firm's longevity. Such findings underscore the importance of contextual analysis, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria, where both internal firm dynamics and external economic pressures interact in complex ways.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of firm attributes on the financial performance of Nigerian listed firms. The specific objectives are:

1. To evaluate the effect of firm size on the financial performance of Nigerian listed firms.
2. To assess the impact of firm age on the financial performance of Nigerian listed firms.

3. To ascertain the effect of leverage and financial performance of Nigerian listed firms.

1.3 Scope of the Study

This study focuses on firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of the most recent reporting period. It covers the period from 2014 to 2023, using secondary data from audited annual reports and financial statements. The study examines firm size and firm age as independent variables and ROA as the dependent variable.

The focus on listed firms is justified by the availability, reliability, and comparability of their financial data, as these firms are required to adhere to regulatory standards, including the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). Also, the timeframe 2014 to 2023 is chosen to allow for a robust longitudinal analysis, capturing both short-term and long-term performance trends across different business cycles, including Nigeria's 2016 recession, 2020–2021 pandemic, and the post-pandemic recovery period, which would have had great impact on the performance of the firms.

2 METHODOLOGY

The study employs an ex post facto research design, suitable for examining historical firm-level financial data without manipulating variables, to investigate the influence of firm attributes, specifically firm size and firm age on financial performance measured by Return on Assets, while controlling for leverage. The population consists of all firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 31, 2023, excluding financial institutions such as banks and insurance companies due to their distinct regulatory and reporting structures. Using a purposive sampling technique, five non-financial firms; Dangote Cement Plc, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Nigerian Breweries Plc, Cadbury Nigeria Plc, and Lafarge Africa Plc were selected based on consistent listing and availability of complete financial data from 2014 to 2023, yielding a final dataset representing approximately 50 non-financial listed firms. The study relies solely on secondary data obtained from audited annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms, supplemented with information from the NGX Factbook and the firms' official websites to ensure reliability and consistency across the 10-year review period.

The data collected for this study were analysed using Pooled Ordinary Least Squares (Pooled OLS) regression estimation technique. To avert the emergency of spurious result, test like descriptive analysis, correlation matrix and unit root test were also conducted on the data.

The study adapted the model by Ilaboya and Ohiokha (2016) who studied firm age, size and profitability dynamics in Nigeria listed firms. The functional form of our model is presented below as;

$$ROA = F(FS, FA, LEV) \quad (1)$$

The econometric form of equation 1 above is presented below as;

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FS_{it} + \beta_2 FA_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + e_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- ROA = Return on Asset (Proxy for firm financial performance)
- $FSIZE$ = Firm Size
- $FAGE$ = Firm Age
- LEV = Financial Leverage

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variable	Type	Measurement
Return on Asset (ROA)	Dependent	Net income ÷ Total assets
Firm Size (FSIZE)	Independent	Natural log of total assets
Firm Age (FAGE)	Independent	Current year minus year of incorporation
Leverage (LEV)	Control	Total debt ÷ Shareholders' equity

Measurement of Variables

Source: Researchers' Compilation

3 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	ROA	FSIZE	FAGE	LEV
Mean	10.60420	19.94600	53.90000	46.53140
Median	11.23500	19.01500	57.00000	49.86000
Maximum	35.47000	26.89000	77.00000	114.0600
Minimum	-30.61000	13.50800	22.00000	3.300000
Std. Dev.	13.75262	4.559305	15.53436	29.66126
Skewness	-0.859058	0.330078	-0.765165	0.200146
Kurtosis	4.303810	1.796352	2.651911	2.228683
Jarque-Bera	9.691335	3.926199	5.131413	1.573257
Observation	50	50	50	50

Source: Researcher's Computation 2025 using Eviews 13

Table 4.1 above shows the result of the descriptive statistics. The mean return on assets is 10.60%, indicating that, on average, the sampled firms generate a profit of 10.60 kobo for every ₦1 of assets invested. The median value of 11.24%, which is slightly higher than the mean, suggests that more than half of the firms in the sample perform marginally better than the average. The maximum ROA recorded is 35.47%, reflecting strong profitability in the best-performing firm, whereas the minimum value of -30.61% implies that some firms incur significant losses.

The standard deviation of 13.75% shows a high dispersion in performance, highlighting large variations in profitability among the firms. The negative skewness of -0.86 indicates that the ROA distribution is left-skewed, suggesting that a larger number of firms have ROA below the mean, pulling the distribution's tail to the left. The kurtosis value of 4.30, which is greater than the normal benchmark of 3, implies that the ROA distribution is leptokurtic it has heavier tails and a sharper peak than a normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 9.69 with a p-value of 0.0079 is statistically significant at the 5% level, implying that the distribution of ROA significantly deviates from normality.

The average firm size, measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, is 19.95, suggesting that the firms in the sample are relatively large. The median value of 19.02 is slightly lower than the mean, indicating a small positive skewness in the distribution. The maximum firm size in the sample is 26.89, while the smallest is 13.51, implying that there is a considerable gap between the largest and smallest firms in terms of total assets.

The average age of firms in the sample is 53.90 years, reflecting that the majority are mature and well-established. The median age is 57 years, which is higher than the mean, indicating that more than half of the firms are older than the average and that the distribution is slightly negatively skewed.

The average leverage ratio is 46.53%, which indicates that firms, on average, finance approximately 47% of their total assets with debt. The highest leverage recorded is 114.06%, which means that some firms are highly indebted, with liabilities exceeding their assets.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix Result

Table 3: Correlation Matrix Result

	ROA	FSIZE	FAGE	LEV
ROA	1	-0.310	-0.509	-0.561
FSIZE	-0.310	1	0.873	0.006
FAGE	-0.509	0.873	1	0.437
LEV	-0.561	0.006	0.437	1

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2025 using Eviews 13

Table 4.3: PP Fisher Chi-Square Pooled Unit Root Test Result

Table 4: PP Fisher Chi-Square Pooled Unit Root Test Result

Variable	Statistics	Probability	Level of Integration	Remark
ROA	36.318	0.0001	I(0)	Stationary
FSIZE	20.381	0.0258	I(0)	Stationary
FAGE	16.014	0.0137	I(1)	Stationary
LEV	30.138	0.0008	I(0)	Stationary

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2025 using Eviews 13

Table 4.4: Pooled OLS Result

Table 5: Pooled OLS Result

Variables	Coefficient	T-Statistics	Prob
FSIZE	-4.085862	-3.138345	0.0032
FAGE	1.585708	2.960627	0.0051
LEV	-0.788164	-8.798142	0.0000

R-Squared 0.718168
Adjusted R-Squared 0.689985
F-Stat (Prob) 25.48212 (0.0000)
DW-Stat 2.338811

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2025 using Eviews 13

Table 4.5: Hypothesis Testing Result

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2025 using Eviews 13

Table 6: Hypothesis Testing Result

Hypothesis	T-Statistics	Probability
Ho1	-3.138345	0.0032
Ho2	2.960627	0.0051
Ho3	-8.798142	0.0000

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the effect of firm attributes on the financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria from 2004 to 2023. Firm size (FSIZE), firm age (FAGE), and leverage (LEV) were used as the independent variables, while return on assets (ROA) was used as the dependent variable. Using pool data and applying Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) analysis method, the result revealed that firm size has a statistically significant negative impact on firm financial performance, firm age has a positive and significant effect on firm financial performance, and leverage exhibits a strong and significant negative relationship with firm financial performance.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Firms should carefully manage growth and expansion to avoid the inefficiencies associated with large organizational size.
2. Older firms should capitalize on their experience by investing in innovation, digital transformation, and market diversification to sustain and improve performance. For younger firms, strategic partnerships and mentorships can help accelerate learning and performance.
3. Corporate managers should reduce excessive reliance on debt financing. Instead, they should explore equity financing and reinvested earnings to fund operations, thereby minimizing the financial burden of interest and reducing risk exposure.

References

- [1] Abubakar, S. (2017). Firm characteristics and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(2), 88–105.
- [2] Adewale, A. R. (2013). Impact of firm size on profitability: A case study of Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(9), 77–84.
- [3] Akanbi, O. A., Ogundipe, O. M., & Ogundipe, L. O. (2020). Firm characteristics and financial performance: Evidence from Nigerian listed firms. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 8(2), 45–59.
- [4] Akintoye, I. R. (2016). Effect of capital structure on firms' performance: The Nigerian experience. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 4(1), 1–17.
- [5] Akinyomi, O. J., & Olagunju, A. (2013). Effect of firm size on profitability: Evidence from Nigerian manufacturing sector. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Studies*, 2(9), 17–23.
- [6] Alabdullah, T. T. Y. (2021). The role of ROA and ROE in evaluating financial performance: Evidence from manufacturing firms. *Journal of Accounting and Investment*, 22(3), 453–467.
- [7] Aladejebi, O. (2021). Firm characteristics and performance of SMEs: Evidence from Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 9(2), 1–12.

- [8] Assefa, D. Z. (2022). Firm size, firm age and business model innovation in response to the COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of International Entrepreneurship*, 20(3), 1–23.
- [9] Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- [10] Becchetti, L., & Trovato, G. (2002). The determinants of growth for small and medium sized firms: The role of the availability of external finance. *Small Business Economics*, 19(4), 291–306.
- [11] Brigham, E. F., & Ehrhardt, M. C. (2017). *Financial management: Theory & practice* (15th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- [12] Coad, A. (2018). *The growth of firms: A survey of theories and empirical evidence*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- [13] Coad, A., Daunfeldt, S.-O., & Halvarsson, D. (2018). Burden or blessing? Firm age, size, and productivity in Swedish manufacturing. *Small Business Economics*, 50(4), 847–865.
- [14] Cowling, M., Liu, W., & Zhang, N. (2018). Did firm age, experience and access to finance count? SME performance after the global financial crisis. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 28(2), 1–27.
- [15] Dogru, T., & Sirakaya-Turk, E. (2018). The effect of firm size on financial performance in the hospitality sector. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76, 20–30.
- [16] Egbunike, F. C., & Ejeabasi, G. N. (2020). Firm characteristics and financial performance: Evidence from listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(1), 45–57.
- [17] Enekwe, C. I., Agu, C. I., & Eziedo, K. N. (2014). The effect of financial leverage on financial performance: Evidence from quoted pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 5(3), 17–25.
- [18] Handoyo, S., Wibowo, A., & Arifin, Z. (2023). Examination of the effects of technology orientation, firm characteristics and performance. *International Journal of Innovation Studies*, 7(1), 45–56.
- [19] Ibrahim, M., & Mansur, Z. (2017). Firm characteristics and financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 8(2), 75–82.
- [20] Idogho, A. M., Ebogbue, C. C., Onmonya, L., & Bosun-Fakunle, Y. F. (2024). Firm characteristics and profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria: The moderating effect of firm size. *International Journal of Accounting & Finance Review*, 11(1), 1–12.
- [21] Ilaboya, O. J., & Ohiokha, F. I. (2016). Firm age, size and profitability dynamics: A test of learning by doing and structural inertia hypotheses in Nigerian quoted firms. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 7(3), 58–72.
- [22] Iorpev, L., & Kwanum, I. M. (2021). Liquidity management and corporate profitability: Evidence from selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 9(2), 19–28.
- [23] Kayo, E. K., & Kimura, H. (2011). Hierarchical determinants of capital structure. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 35(2), 358–371.

- [24] Kraus, S., Harms, R., & Schwarz, E. J. (2010). Strategic planning in smaller enterprises: New empirical findings. *Management Research News*, 33(5), 419–432.
- [25] Loderer, C., Stulz, R. M., & Waelchli, U. (2017). Firm age and investment. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 124(3), 471–490.
- [26] Mallinguh, E., Wasike, C., & Zoltan, Z. (2020). The business sector, firm age, and performance: The mediating role of foreign ownership and financial leverage. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(11), 1–18.
- [27] Miller, R. A., & Friesen, P. H. (1984). A longitudinal study of the corporate life cycle. *Management Science*, 30(10), 1161–1183.
- [28] Myers, S. C., & Majluf, N. S. (1984). Corporate financing and investment decisions: When firms have information that investors do not have. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 13(2), 187–221.
- [29] Niresh, J. A., & Velnampy, T. (2014). Firm size and profitability: A study of listed manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(4), 57–64.
- [30] Odugbesan, J. A., & Ajao, M. G. (2022). Firm characteristics and financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing companies. *African Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 11(4), 521–537.
- [31] Ogundipe, L. O., Adebisi, A. A., & Akanbi, T. A. (2020). Firm-specific characteristics and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 6(1), 1–11.
- [32] Okafor, C., & Ejike, E. I. (2019). Determinants of financial performance of firms in Nigeria: An empirical review. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 5(3), 10–19.
- [33] Okoye, P. V. C., Evbuomwan, G. O., & Modebe, N. J. (2016). Effect of firm characteristics on financial performance of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(2), 65–73.
- [34] Omenyo, D. M., & Muturi, W. (2019). Effect of firm size on financial performance of manufacturing firms listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 6(4), 1112–1119.
- [35] Onyekwelu, U. L., & Ugwuanyi, U. B. (2020). Firm age, size and performance of quoted firms in Nigeria: A sectoral analysis. *International Journal of Academic Accounting, Finance & Management Research*, 4(3), 33–49.
- [36] Oyelade, O. A. (2019). The impact of firm size on firm's performance in Nigeria: A comparative study of selected firms in the building industry. *Asian Development Policy Review*, 7(1), 1–11.
- [37] Penrose, E. T. (1959). *The theory of the growth of the firm*. Oxford University Press.
- [38] Ross, S. A., Westerfield, R., & Jaffe, J. (2019). *Corporate finance* (12th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- [39] Rossi, M. (2016). Determinants of financial performance in emerging markets. *International Journal of Business Research*, 16(3), 35–46.
- [40] Uwalomwa, U., Uwuigbe, U., & Oyewo, B. M. (2015). Corporate governance and financial performance of banks: A study of listed banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Auditing: Research & Practice*,

2015, 1–8.

- [41] Wernerfelt, B. (1984). A resource-based view of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5(2), 171–180.
- [42] Yahaya, K. A., Yusuf, M. B. O., & Dania, I. A. (2015). Effect of firm characteristics on financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(11), 1037–1055.